

CLASSIFICATION OF YOGAM AND EXPLANATION OF PARIVARTHANAI (TRANSACTION OF PLANETS) YOGAM

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Abstract:

Astrology speaks many types and kinds of Yogam. Same way in Astrology Yogam means conjunction of minimum two planets or you can say that, any interaction between two planets, transacting in any Bhava or more is involved. In this research study we are going through the types and kinds of Yogams, explained in many Vedic original texts, also particularly going to explain what is PARIVARTHANAI / TRANSACTION YOGAM and impacts in any Natal Chart.

Key Words: Yogam, Parivarthanai, Charam, Ishtiram, Upayam, Ascendant

Parivarthana:

Parivarthanai / Transaction of planets means – any two planets inter changed with respect to their own House depends from Ascendant. There should be Right/Direct-positive Angular/Shadow Negative. Under this rule transaction between 1-5-9 and 4,7,10 deities are in any natal chart they will rule the world. If Lagnathipathy in 11th place, and the Deity 11th house in Ascendant, and the Lord of 2 sits in 10th house, and the Lord of 10th house site in 2 house (He/she) will enjoy the life like a King and have the life of Lord Indiran, which means in will lead a healthy and happy life.

Classification of Yogam:

Yogam classified in three categories. They are as follows

- Positive Transaction of Planets
- Negative Transaction of Planets
- Both Positive and Negative Transaction

If Transaction of planet happened in between 1, 5 and 9 and when the Dasa Bukthi activates will get Positive and beneficial results. If Parivarthanai take place between these places, then the person will get Positive benefits. Normally transaction between Jupiter in Cancer and the Moon in Pisces will give positive and life like King to the Natal chart. In total the Exchange between 1, 5, 9th places, will lead to 'AADHI PATHYA KARMA' benefits and the benefited planets are 1, 4, 7 & 10 with beneficial. But, the transactions held between the Jupiter in Cancer and the Moon in Sagittarius will give unbeneficial or Negative results. Same way the transactions between Sun and Saturn leads Negative result.

Pala Deepikai the Original Vedic Text classified as 66 types of Yogas as follows:

DHYNYA YOHAM	30
KALA YOHAM	8
MAHARA YOHAM	28
TOTAL	66

While the Bava of 2 -12 in the position of transaction, and the planets receives or touch with Bad elements (negative bavas) there will be only negative results. If BHAVAS and BHAVATHIPATHIES are in POSITIVE POSITION, then the result will be beneficial. But the bava transaction of 3 and 11 will give maximum of Positive and beneficial minimum negative.

Transaction Beneficial of 3 and 11:

(1-3, 2-4, 3-5, 4-6, 5-7, 6-8, 7-9, 8-10, 9-11, 10-12, 2-12)

In this 3-11, transaction Benefits are based on bavath to bava (3-11) which are interlinked with upachaya (improvement) houses, transaction between Bavath Bava Lords, Right and Left movements. In this aspect the efforts of the beneficiary plays an important Role in bringing out a great success. They are assisted by Friends and Relatives. He achieves all by his own efforts to the higher stage. This 3-11 transaction will give the result of only benefits.

Transaction According to Kala Purusha Principles:

LIBRA	-	SUN	WILL GET NEGATIVE BENEFITS
LEO	-	VEENUS	NEGATIVE APPROCH
ACQUARIS	-	MARS	BETWEEN - BHAVAS
AIRES	-	SATURN	will get only Negative long fits

Transaction Benefits between 4-10:

(1-4, 2-5, 3-6, 4-7,5-8, 6-9, 7-10, 8-11, 9-12, 10-1, 11-2, 12-3)

These exchanges are comes under 4-10 Transaction, There are some negative benefits will Occur due to exchange between ODD digit and Evan digit Rasis. Due to weak strength of RASI and Graha's (MARS-AND-SATURN) 4-10 facing eachother and the movements 56 SUB RASI Moving Rasi and Static Rasis will give POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE Benefits to the beneficiary.

Note:

MERCURY & JUPITOR WILL NOT GIVE Transaction Benefits

Transaction Benefits of 1-5:

The transactions between the houses of 1-5, 2-6, 3-7, 4-8, 5-9, 6-10, 7-11, 8-12, 9-1, 10-2, 11-3, 12-4 comes under this group. The Transaction benefits under BHAVATH to BHAVA basis 1-5; stands in ANGULAR direction. Also between 5-9, will have friendly Relations, and will bestow boosted yogams to the beneficiary. Same way the transaction of 5-1, 9-5 will also give good Benefits.

SCORPIO	-	SATURN	
CAPRICON	-	SATURN	WILL REFLECT HIGHEST, POSITIVE
CAPRICON	-	MARS	BENEFITS
TAURUS	-	MOON	
CANCER	-	VEENUS	RIGHT TO LEFT MOVEMENT
TAURUS	-	JUPITER	NO NEGATIVE RESULTS.
PISES	-	VEENUS	
LIBRA	-	SUN	WILL GET NEGATIVE BENEFITS
LEO	-	VEENUS	NEGATIVE APPROCH
ACQUARIS	-	MARS	BETWEEN BHAVAS
AIRES	-	SATU	will give only Negative long fits

CANCER + MARS		In these two combinations,
SCORPIO + MOON		only NEGATIVE benefit available.
MOON + MARS		DASA BUKTHF – Will lead to hectic –
		Mental / physical
SINGLE DIGIT / ODD DIGIT	-	Transaction benefits – INTERNAL
		PERGONAL / IMMATERTAL

Transaction Benefits of 6-8:

(1-6, 2-7, 3-8, 4-9, 5-10, 6-11, 7-12, 8-1, 9-2, 10-3, 11-4, 12-5) are grouped under this category

Family love & affection relationship spoiled, not in good term, struggles in house, lack of education, land dispute, acquires of ancestral properties. Hindrance in getter profit from Inductor, exchange of properties. Even though there are great possibility of huge PROFIT but available to enjoy or acquit, immediate loss, Children Health affected, Prestige will be badly affected.

- 6-11 Problem everywhere – handles and delayed attitude. Restriction against sexual Relation, brothers enormity –problems in partnership breaking
- 8-1 Extended life – facing problem with handles Life will be always miserable, but principled life / man.
- 9-2 Ancestral wealth, Father, money Problem, family problem, court case.
- 10-3 Humiliate, prestige affected, bad name character criticisms, changes in profession assault court leads to self-made problems.
- 11-4 Restrictions to enjoy sexual benefits, house, car, loans against property, no steady economic condition.

Transaction benefits of 12-5, Ancestral property and other problems in plenty, worsening of children health. If both Lord of Houses are affected, by its power and MOON is also affected, then there will be Mental problem. He/she will be Psychic. Problem between brothers on higher side. MOSTLY AFFECTED RAASIES ARE: CANCER, LEO, COPRICON, ACQUARIS

AIRES	-	SCORPIO Lagnam Holders – people are not affected
TAURUS	-	LIBRA by this exchange benefit

Transaction Benefits of: (1-7, 2-8, 3-9, 4-10, 5-11, 6-12)

JUPITER-MERCURY, SUN - SATURAN , MOON – SAT, MARS – VEENUS : Most of the Transaction between Rasies from 1to7, where change takes place with virus of Graha Angular direction – enmity will riches INCREASED BENEFITS. But Negative effects due to opposite Graha exchange.

For Example:

VEENUS – MARS – disputes between Husband & Wife SUN – SATURAN – disputes between Father & Child.

Sara Parivarthanai – Linked Mutual Exchanges:

Interchange of Qualities between Grahas:

Transaction of internal qualities between Grahas with one another one after another in called SARA PARIVARTHANAI. According to Law of Grahas it will always give its own benefits to the concerned, It may be promotional, highlighted and Best, or detachment or poor / or negative benefits based on the relationship of the person Graha’s place, friendship, enmity, status etc.

Part 2 - Even Digit Exchange Benefits:

Combination Group Benefits (1-4, 2-5, 3-6, 4-7, 5-8, 6-9, 7-10, 8-11, 9-12, 10-1, 11-2, 12-3) : Transaction between ODD & EVEN DIGITS RAASIES will effect NEGATIVE BENEFITS. Due to poor strength between Grahas – Planets MARS & SATURN are available in SUB RASI, MOBILE RASI and STATIC RAASI. Will give positive and Negative benefits to the beneficiary.

Note: MARS AND JUPITOR WILL NOT GIVE EXCHANGE BENEFITS.

General Rule:

The combination of ODD DIGIT Exchange in related to IMMATERIAL	INTERNAL Grahas PERSONNEL
The combination of EVEN DIGIT Exchange benefits related to MATERIAL	EXTERNAL Graha IMPERSONNEL

Combination of 6-8 Benefits:

Group : (1-6, 2-7, 3-8, 4-9, 5-10, 6-11, 7-12, 8-1, 9-2, 10-3, 11-4, 12-5)

According to BHATH BHAVA Principles 6-8 under combination –Lagnathipathy stander in 6th place and the lord of 6th House stand in 8th House / Lagnaw. They give only BAD effects. This is due to their position in ODD & EVEN place. Their views are ANGULAR and in SHADOW Region which related to AADHIPATHYA – KARMA – and also problems with negative results with delayed process.

GROUP	RESULTS
Disease, court case, Loan problem enmity among brothers.	2-7
Problem in family, PARJNESHID & EYE defects	3-8
Fear of life, Multiple problems, difference of opinion between brothers.	4-9
Problem between Father – child lack of love between parents, education, land problem, Ancestral properties	5-10
Barriers in beginners, change in business, even though RAJA YOHAM (High Return) but sudden loss, disgrace and humiliated, children health affected	6-11
Problem are everywhere and any where only Barriers – delay.	7-12
Barriers to sexual happiness – difference of opinion between Husband and wife separation in business and part nasty. Life Extension, battling effect, struggle but people are principled	2-9
Ancestral problem, money family problem, quarries, court case.	3-10
Undue band name, shameful incident character criticism, Due to assault and lethargic attitude one has to face problems of their own. Barriers to enjoyment of self profits family benefits, movable / immovable loan everywhere – normal economic condition.	5-12
Ancestors default will be on the higher side children health will be affected – dissolved mental stability – mentally affected problem due to BAD POSITION OF MOON (NEECHA – MOON). Leader problem between Husband and wife, Father, Mother, Brother.	

Benefits Under Sub (Ubaya cga) Raasies:

Combination of JUPITOR AND MERCURY Under exchange benefits under ODD & EVEN Raasies (Starting) will give ONLY BAD BENEFITS which are related to BHATHAHATHIBATHI YOHAM, KENDRATHIPATHY YOHAM AND MAARAHATHE YOHAM. Thosha related benefits are only available. Exchange benefits under 6-8 places will give only Negative benefits. Out of 66 Exchange benefits 1-5 combination GEMNI – VIRGO MERCURY – SAGGRITUS – PISES – GURU exchange will give great positive favorable benefits. The other combinations will give mixed benefits bad benefits only available.

In exchange under 6-8 always reflect bad benefits unless and until if the combinations are not affected by Exchange Bhava’s Graha’s and its positions are in good relation, then only, beneficiary will get good benefits.

According to “BALA THEEBIGAI” – Under chapter 6, sloka 28 PARIVARTHAAI YOHAS ARE Defined as follows.

DHANYA MAHA YOHAM	30
KALA MAHA YOHAM	28

MAHA YOHA	8
TOTAL	66

Dhanya Maha Yohams:

Lord of 12th House standing in, 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12 = 12

Sthanathepathi 12 in 6th place : 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 1, 2, 3, 4 = 10

Lord of 8 stands in – 9, 10, 11, 12, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7 & 8 = 9

Total = 30

Lord of 3 stands in 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12 and the other Lord standing in 3 rd place.

KALA YOHA = 28

We are getting 66 Exchange benefits due to the Exchange of place from LAGNAM TO 12 Places and from one place to another vice versa. They are Totally classified into THREE Groups.

- 8th Lagnathipathy stands in 2, 4, 5, 7, 9, 11
- 2nd Lord stands in 4, 5, 7, 9, 11 and the Lord of the respective house stands in 2
- 4th Lord stands in 5, 7, 9, 10, 11 and the Lords of respective house stands in 4th house
- 5th Lord stands in 7, 9, 10, 11 and the Lords of respective house stands in 5th house
- 7th Lord stands in 9, 10, 11 and the Lords of respective house stands in 7th house
- 9th Lord stands in 10, 11 and the Lords of respective house stands in 9th house
- 10th Lord stands in 11 and the Lords of respective house stands in 10th house so to conclude YOHAMS – 28+8+30 = 66

Benefits of Thynya Yoham:

He/she – Horoshious – Do all sinly attitude – Talk abuse words – wavering minded – Never attempt – any work fully.

Benefits under Kala Yoham:

He/she will receive positive benefits, and enjoy merits. Sometimes they do good things. They enjoy positive and Negative benefits.

Benefits under Maha Yoham:

He/she bestowed characters – worship able appearance flourish had with wealth ornaments, movable and immovable properties and will bad luxurious life.

In Parasara Horai – Bhavathipathi Bathi's – their change of places will be in geomantic properties it means 12x12 = 144 type of benefits. Mostly they are bended by KARAHA Benefits. But in interchange of MOON Vs SATURN – they NEVER GIVE POSITIVE BENEFITS. During their course of DASHA BUKTHI Stages, they are FORCED TO TURN LIFE FROM FAMILY TO SANYASAM.

According to Kalapurusha Principles:

If a person He/she, due to POORVA JENMA PUNYA'S who attains birth under the following RAASIES – AIRES, TAURUS, LEO, VIRGO, SAGGITARUS, CAPRICON, when these Raasies exchanges with Graha's gets FIRST CLASS Benefits.

Along with thes Raasies – CANCER, PISES, SCORPIO, when exchanges with Grahas get – medium – equal benefits. Transaction between Gemini, LIBRA, ACQUARIS, Rasai standing in respective graha's will give only lower grade benefits (3rd class benefits) with this PISES-LIBRA-ACQUARIS- transaction benefits, if they are have DUSH – KARMA, then they will get only BAD / NEGATIVE Benefits. And if they are having SATH-KARMA, then they will get GOOD BENEFITS.

PLEASE FOLLOW THE RULES CAREFULLY STATED ABOVE WHILE ANALYSING WITH HOROSCOPES ON its MERITS AND DEMERITS.

In experience you can understand RAASIES under AIRES, LEO, SAGGRITIS, TAURUS, VIRGO AND CAPRICON Under Rasi 1, 4, 5, 7, 9, 10, 11 in transaction will get POSITIVE BENEFITS Under 2, 3, 6, 8, 12 will get affected benefits.

CANCER, SCORPIO, PISES, GEMINI, LIBRA and Acquires while interchange will not get good benefits permanently. when transaction between 2, 3, 6, 8, 12 will get barred effect is applicable not Nourishing.

Conclusion:

As we explained above, about PARIVARTHANAI Yogam, its classifications, types and kinds of yogam, the rues involved and its implication. However, the Parivarthanai Yogam is one of best of its kind and easy to analyze from any Natal chart. Also while on prediction the Yogam is easy to ruled out and predict by one who knows well about the Bava and the Bavathipathy. By this yogam on any horoscope, the particular person is going to enjoy or not, or will be beneficial or unbeneficial is to be depends on Natal Chart and the particular planets occupied the position which is to be drawn be clear calculations.

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